

Supplementary material for

Spatially-resolved analysis of tebuconazole penetration in wood using desorption electrospray ionisation mass spectrometry imaging

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Fig. S. 1. DESI source set-up for block samples with marked geometrical parameters (α - incidence angle, d_1 - sprayer-to-surface distance, d_2 - inlet-to-surface distance, d_3 - sprayer-to-inlet distance).

Fig. S. 2. Representative spectrum of the area on the wood to which tebuconazole was applied.

Table. S. 1. Summary of the m/z values corresponding only with the area of TBC application on wood. For each ion, the experimentally observed m/z value is reported together with its relative intensity, the proposed elemental composition and rational formula based of MS experiments. The corresponding theoretical m/z values and calculated mass deviations in mDa are also provided. Relative intensities were rounded to the nearest 5 or 10% to reflect reproducibility error.

Observed m/z value	Proposed elemental composition	Theoretical m/z value	Mass error [mDa]	Relative intensity [%]	Proposed ion formula
308.1524	C16H23N3OCl	308.153	-0.6	100	[M+H] ⁺
281.1417	C15H22N2OCl	281.1421	-0.4	90	[M+H-27] ⁺
346.1084	C16H22N3OClK	346.1088	-0.4	20	[M+K] ⁺
588.2873	C31H44N5O2Cl2	588.2872	0.1	20	[2M-26] ⁺
330.1342	C16H22N3OClNa	330.1349	-0.7	5	[M+Na] ⁺

The ion at m/z 281.1417 is tentatively assigned to a neutral loss of 27 Da from [M+H]⁺, consistent with triazole-related fragmentation. The ion at m/z 588.29 is tentatively assigned as a dimeric (cluster) ion.

Fig. S. 3. Schematic representation of the segmentation approach used for the semi-quantitative DESI-MSI analysis of tebuconazole in wood. The analysed wood cross-sections were divided into consecutive segments of 0.6 mm width along the longitudinal axis, each spanning the full lateral extent of the imaged area. This segmentation was used to extract average ion intensities of the tebuconazole pseudo-molecular signal for depth-resolved semi-quantitative analysis.

Fig. S. 4. Depths of thresholds of TBC in wood samples from series E and F as a function of analyte concentration. Points represent threshold depths for each sample, with dashed lines representing linear regressions fitted to the data for each series.